

Electrical Conductivity Studies on Alumina-Zinc-Oxide Catalysts

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Studies on the chemisorption of ethanol vapour and hydrogen and the accompanying electrical conductivity changes on pure as well as mixed alumina-zinc oxide catalysts were carried out in the temperature range 50°–220°C. The catalyst pellets were degassed for a long time (about 12 hours) at 500° and the conductivity measurements were carried out during ethanol adsorption at temperatures of 50°, 80°, 120°, 150°, and 180° while with hydrogen adsorption the conductivity measurements were made at 50°, 90°, 140°, 160°, 180° and 220°. The conductivity isobars showed an increase in conductivity during ethanol adsorption at all temperatures; the corresponding increase in conductivity with hydrogen adsorption was observed in the temperature range 140°–220°C.

The results have been discussed in terms of the conductivity type of the catalysts and the electronic features of the reacting species. It has been shown that the degassing temperature of the catalyst is important in determining the surface conductivity.

As part of their overall study of the mechanism of the simultaneous dehydration-dehydrogenation of ethanol leading to butadiene formation, Bhattacharyya, *et al.*¹ have recently carried out investigations on the chemisorption and electrical conductivity of alumina-zinc oxide catalyst which had earlier been reported by them² to be superior to other catalysts studied by them. Their results on the conductivity measurements on alumina-zinc oxide catalysts which had been degassed at 400° showed that the conductivity of the catalysts decreased in ethanol atmosphere in the temperature range 60°–250°; contrary to the earlier results of Bielanski and coworkers³ that the conductivity of n-type catalysts, increased in ethanol atmosphere while that of p-type catalysts decreased.

In view of this and also because of the recent findings of Molinari and others⁴ about the change in the nature of conductivity of zinc oxide catalysts with a change in the degassing temperature, it was considered necessary to carry out the experiments with catalysts degassed at higher temperatures. Accordingly, the conductivity measurements were carried out during ethanol adsorption with catalysts degassed at 500°. As hydrogen is one of the products of the reaction, conductivity measurements were carried out during hydrogen adsorption also with a view to get some idea about the conductivity characteristics of the alumina-zinc oxide catalysts.

EXPERIMENTAL

The preparation of the catalysts and the purification of ethanol and hydrogen were carried out following the methods described earlier¹.

1. S. K. Bhattacharyya, K. S. De, S. N. Pandao and G. V. Chandrasekhar, *Proc. 3rd. Intern. Congr. on Catalysis, Amsterdam*, 1964, **1**, 474–483.
2. S. K. Bhattacharyya and N. D. Ganguly, *J. Appld. Chem.*, 1962, **12**, 97, 105. S. K. Bhattacharyya and B. N. Avasthi: *I & E. C. Process and Design Development*, 1963, **2**, 45.
3. A. Bielanski, J. Deren, J. Haber and J. Sloczynski, *Proc. 2nd. Intern. Congr. on Catalysis, Paris*, 1960.
4. A. Cimino, E. Molinari and F. Caramrossa, *J. Catalysis*, 1963, **2**, 315–323.

The conductivity measurements of the pellets during ethanol and hydrogen chemisorption were carried out as reported previously¹.

RESULTS

The conductivity data were obtained only for pure zinc oxide and 20 : 80 alumina-zinc oxide as the very high initial resistances (more than 500 megohm) of the other alumina-zinc oxide catalysts prevented any accurate measurement of conductivity changes being made.

The catalyst pellets made by compressing the sample under pressure and having a density of 4.003 were degassed for a long time (about twelve hours) at 500° and the conductivity measurements were carried out during ethanol adsorption at temperatures of 50°, 80°, 120°, 150° and 180°C. It was observed that the conductivity of the catalyst samples increased in ethanol atmosphere. The results of the conductivity measurements at different temperatures are shown as isobars in Fig. 1 at a constant pressure of 30 mms of mercury.

FIG. 1.

Conductivity isobars for ethanol adsorption. Pressure of ethanol vapour 30 mms of mercury.

O = Al₂O₃ : ZnO = 20 : 80

○ = Al₂O₃ : ZnO = 0 : 100

Catalysts degassed at 500°

$\left(\frac{\Delta C}{C}\right)\%$ = Percentage change in conductivity

In the case of hydrogen chemisorption the conductivity measurements were carried out at 50°, 90°, 140°, 160°, 180°, and 220°C. While at 50° and 90° there was no change in conductivity with hydrogen adsorption, at the other temperatures the conductivity increased with hydrogen pressure. The conductivity isobars at a constant hydrogen pressure of 300 mms are shown in Fig. 2.

FIG. 2.

Conductivity isobars for hydrogen adsorption. Pressure of hydrogen 300 mms of mercury.

O = Al₂O₃ : ZnO = 20 : 80

● = Al₂O₃ : ZnO = 0 : 100

A survey of literature published earlier^{3,5} shows that ethanol usually behaves as an electron donor and hence adsorption of ethanol on zinc-oxide and alumina-zinc oxide catalysts which are usually n-type semi-conductors should be accompanied by an increase in conductivity. Contrary to the general expectation the authors reported earlier¹ that when the degassing temperature was 400°C, the conductivity of the catalyst sample decreased in presence of ethanol. In the present investigation, using catalysts degassed at a higher temperature (500°), the authors observed that the conductivity increased in ethanol atmosphere as is normally expected (Fig. 1). The probable reasons for these results can be discussed taking into account the fact that the direction of conductivity change depends on two factors: the type of semiconductivity of the catalyst and the electronic features of the reacting species.

It is quite possible that zinc oxide and alumina-zinc oxide samples prepared in air behave as if they were of p-character. Treatment of the samples in high vacuum at 500°C, completely removes the surface p-type layer and the n-character is restored. This type of surface p-type behaviour of zinc oxide samples and the change over to n-type behaviour when the degassing temperature is increased from 450° to 500°C have been observed by Cimino, *et al.*⁴ during their experiments on oxygen adsorption on zinc oxide. Such

p-type conduction has also been observed by Rudolph⁶ but only for polycrystalline rods of zinc oxide, strongly doped with lithium (2%) and at high temperatures (750°), and the possibility of surface p-type conduction in zinc oxide in an oxygen atmosphere has been theoretically envisaged by Krusemeyer and Thomas⁷.

Fresh samples of zinc oxide are characterised by almost stoichiometric surfaces with a comparatively high concentration of chemisorbed oxygen and an inversion layer of p-type zinc oxide may be formed at the surface by chemisorption of weakly bonded oxygen. But it would seem that introduction of alcohol would immediately remove this oxygen thus restoring the n-type behaviour, which in fact was observed by Bielanski and coworkers³. Moreover, the results of hydrogen adsorption experiment show that the conductivity of both zinc oxide and alumina-zinc oxide catalysts increased in hydrogen atmosphere irrespective of degassing temperature, implying thereby that the catalysts are essentially of n-type character.

The idea that positive holes might contribute to the surface conductivity of fresh samples of zinc oxides receives further support from the work of Gray⁸, who suggests that both donor levels and acceptor levels are present in zinc oxide and that probably both are important in influencing the chemisorption of gases. Chemisorption of ethanol, with donation of electrons to the surface, would reduce the conductivity by partial annihilation of positive holes. A similar explanation has been suggested to account for the decrease in conductivity of zinc oxide by carbon monoxide adsorption⁹. But again, it is difficult to explain on the basis of this mechanism, the results of hydrogen adsorption observed in the present investigation.

All these considerations are valid only on the assumption that the adsorbed species acts as donor of electrons. The observed change in conductivity reflects only the net effect of transfer of electrons between the surface of the oxide and all kinds of adsorbed species. In the system alcohol-metal oxide, not only the possibility of the adsorption of alcohol in various forms must be taken into account, but also the possibility of adsorption of various products of its decomposition as well as its influence on the oxygen coverage. In consequence a number of interrelated equilibria may be established at the surface, which depend on the conditions of the experiment, as well as on the pretreatment of the oxide and it is difficult to predict whether the adsorbed layer as a whole would eventually behave as a donor or acceptor of electrons. If there are different species adsorbed, some of them being electron donors and some electron acceptors, the mere shifting of the surface equilibria may entail the inversion of the conductivity change direction.

Of the different species adsorbed during dehydration-dehydrogenation of ethanol, ethanol has been found to be generally electron donating while ethylene and ether have not been investigated. Bielanski and coworkers³ have found that water vapour did not have any effect on the conductivity of n- and p-type samples indicating that either water was not chemisorbed or less probably, was chemisorbed without electron transfer. In the

6. V. J. Rudolph, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1959, **14a**, 727.

7. H. J. Krusemeyer and D. G. Thomas, *J. Phys. & Chem. of Solids*, 1958, **4**, 78.

8. T. J. Gray, "Defect Solid State" (Ed: Gray) Interscience Publishers, New York, 1957, 274.

9. T. S. Nagarjunan, Ph.D. Thesis, I.I.T., Kharagpur, India, 1959.

case of acetaldehyde, Bielanski and coworkers³ have found that acetaldehyde acts as donor of electrons. According to Volkenstein¹⁰ acetaldehyde can act both as donor or acceptor of electrons and that the donor or acceptor character of chemisorption is determined by what bond in the molecule is saturated by surface valency.

The difference between the zinc oxide samples outgassed at 400° and at 500°C is probably only in the coverage of the surface with oxygen. Samples of zinc oxide degassed at 400°C still contain quite a lot of oxygen adsorbed which is being removed to a large extent on outgassing at 500°C. It may well be that on an oxidised surface the adsorbed species are different than on a deoxidised surface, or they behave in a different way.

It is obvious from the above remarks that before any explanation can be given as to the role of the alumina-zinc oxide catalysts in the simultaneous dehydration-dehydrogenation of ethanol leading to butadiene formation, further work on the electron donating or accepting characteristics of the different species involved, have to be investigated thoroughly.

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